

SPECIAL ISSUE

JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ
ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

VOLUME II | ISSUE 3 | MAY-JUNE | 2024

ISSN: 2181-4031

Available online at www.imfaktor.com

ISSN: 2181-4031
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4031

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

II-ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ- II, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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ТОШКЕНТ – 2024

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ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

№ 3 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.56017/2181-4031-2024-3>

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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11518862>

THE LEGAL NATURE OF HARASSMENT AS A TYPE OF ENCROACHMENT ON THE PERSONAL INVIOABILITY, HONOR, DIGNITY AND PRIVACY OF A CITIZEN

ANNOTATION

This academic article provides a comprehensive overview of the legal regulation of harassment across various countries, including the United Kingdom, Switzerland, Denmark, Czech Republic, Australia, Israel, India, Philippines, Argentina, and Georgia. It examines the evolution of laws, definitions of harassment, penalties for violations, and the responsibilities of employers and individuals. The analysis highlights the diverse approaches to combating harassment globally, reflecting each country's cultural and societal context.

Keywords: harassment, legislation, United Kingdom, Switzerland, Denmark, Czech Republic, Australia, Israel, India, Philippines.

ПРАВОВАЯ ПРИРОДА ДОМОГАТЕЛЬСТВА КАК ВИДА ПОСЯГАТЕЛЬСТВА НА ЛИЧНУЮ НЕПРИКОСНОВЕННОСТЬ, ЧЕСТЬ, ДОСТОИНСТВО И НЕПРИКОСНОВЕННОСТЬ ЧАСТНОЙ ЖИЗНИ ГРАЖДАНИНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой научной статье представлен всесторонний обзор правового регулирования домогательств в различных странах, включая Великобританию, Швейцарию, Данию, Чехию, Австралию, Израиль, Индию, Филиппины, Аргентину и Грузию. В нем рассматривается эволюция законов, определения домогательств, наказания за нарушения и обязанности работодателей и частных лиц. Анализ выявляет различные подходы к борьбе с домогательствами во всем мире, отражающие культурный и социальный контекст каждой страны.

Ключевые слова: домогательства, законодательство, Великобритания, Швейцария, Дания, Чехия, Австралия, Израиль, Индия, Филиппины.

ТАЗЙИҚНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАБИАТИ ФУҚАРОНИНГ ШАХСИЙ ДАХЛСИЗЛИГИ, ШАЪНИ, ҚАДР-ҚИММАТИ ВА ШАХСИЙ ҲАЁТИГА ТАЖОВУЗ ҚИЛИШ ТУРИ СИФАТИДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Бу илмий мақола турли мамлакатларда бўйлаб таъкиб ҳуқуқий тартибга солиш кенг камровли умумий беради, Буюк Британия, шу жумладан, Швейцария, Дания, Чехия Республикаси, Австралия, Исроил, Ҳиндистон, Филиппин, Argentina, ва Грузия. Унда қонунларнинг эволюцияси, таъкиб қилиш таърифлари, қоидабузарликлар учун жазолар, иш берувчилар ва жисмоний шахсларнинг мажбуриятлари кўриб чиқилади. Таҳлилда ҳар бир мамлакатнинг маданий ва ижтимоий контекстини ақс еттирувчи global миқёсда таъкибларга қарши курашнинг турли ёндашувлари таъкидланган.

Калит сўзлар: таъкиб, Қонунчилик, Буюк Британия, Швейцария, Дания, Чехия, Австралия, Исроил, Ҳиндистон, Филиппин.

1. *THE CONCEPT AND ESSENCE OF THE RIGHT TO PERSONAL INVIOABILITY, HONOR, DIGNITY, AND PRIVATE LIFE*

It should be noted that for the first time, the right to personal inviolability was established in the legislation of Great Britain within the framework of the "Habeas Corpus Act" in the 17th century. Subsequently, in the 18th century, this right was proclaimed in the French "Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen" of 1789 and the U.S. Bill of Rights of 1791. To elucidate the legal definition of this term, it is necessary to refer to a number of international acts adopted in the 20th century.

Currently, this right is regulated by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in Paris on December 10, 1948. It served as the first document in the history of mankind to proclaim the necessity of protecting human rights. Thus, Article 3 of this act regulates that everyone has the right to personal inviolability. In legal doctrine, personal inviolability is understood as the inadmissibility of external unlawful influence on the sphere of an individual's life activities, including physical and psychological inviolability. This right is guaranteed by a set of legal norms and mechanisms of protection, providing for the impermissibility of encroachments on the individual from outside, except as provided by law.

Every person, along with the inalienable right to personal inviolability, possesses the fundamental right to freedom; these complementary rights are also reflected in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted by the General Assembly on December 16, 1966. By ratifying these two documents on September 30, 1991, the Republic of Uzbekistan reflected this norm in Article 25 of its Constitution. According to the glossary of the textbook on Constitutional Law edited by I.T.

Tulyteyev, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, personal inviolability is understood as the requirement of the inadmissibility of any interference from outside in the sphere of a person's private life, including encroachments on their personal freedom. Based on this provision of the Basic Law, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Article 99 established that personal inviolability pertains to personal non-property rights belonging to a citizen from birth or by law, which are inalienable and cannot be transferred in any other way.

This postulate once again emphasizes that the right to personal inviolability is of fundamental importance, as it is one of the most important human rights and must be guaranteed by the state. An equally significant social good is the right of a citizen to honor and dignity. These two categories of ethics, which are closely interconnected, are often considered together as they complement each other.

According to a prominent legal dictionary, honor is the societal moral evaluation of a person, while dignity is a moral and ethical category signifying respect and self-esteem of the human individual. Professor Rustambaev views honor as the objective societal opinion, a specific social assessment of an individual. Dignity, on the other hand, reflects this quality in the consciousness of the individual, i.e., self-assessment based on the societal opinion about them.

The preamble of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that recognizing the dignity and worth of human beings is the foundation of freedom, justice, and universal peace, fostering social progress and improving living conditions. Articles 1 and 12 of these documents stipulated that all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights, and no one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with their honor.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan reflected these norms in Article 19, stating that democracy in Uzbekistan is based on universal human principles, with the highest value being the individual, their life, freedom, honor, dignity, and other inalienable rights. In Chapter VII of the Constitution, personal rights and freedoms are defined, and according to Article 26, everyone has the right to protection against encroachments on their honor and dignity. Article 60 of the legal act emphasizes that citizens are obliged to comply with the Constitution and laws, respect the rights, freedoms, honor, and dignity of others. These constitutional principles found their reflection in the corresponding articles of civil legislation. For instance, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan more elaborately regulates issues of protecting the honor and dignity of citizens. Referring again to Article 99 of this Code, it can be noted that honor and dignity, along with personal inviolability, belong to personal non-material rights inherent to a citizen from birth or by law, which are not alienable or transferable in any other way. Article 100 of the Code defines the procedure for protecting a citizen in case of dissemination of information that tarnishes their honor, dignity, or business reputation.

Another fundamental human right is the right to privacy. This right was not enshrined in the Roman-Germanic legal tradition for many centuries. The term "privacy" emerged in the late 19th century in the United States in an article by Samuel Warren and Louis Brandeis titled "The Right to Privacy," published in 1860, which became a legal doctrine classic.

Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights established that no one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with their privacy. A similar norm is reflected in Article 17 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in turn, indicated in Article 17 the impermissibility of interference in private life. According to the textbook of Constitutional Law edited by I.T. Tulyev, private life comprises those aspects of a person's personal life that they, by virtue of their freedom, do not wish to share with others. This is a kind of personal sovereignty, indicating the inviolability of their "habitat". It is summarized that privacy does not conceal any anti-social or unlawful activity. It reflects the natural desire of every person to have their own world of personal and business interests hidden from others. Article 99 of the Civil Code defines that privacy, private and family secrets, belong to personal non-material rights inherent to a citizen from birth or by law, which are not alienable or transferable in any other way. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the institute of privacy encompasses several rules and guarantees, characterized as follows:

- Individuals have the right to personal and family secrets, and the protection of their honor. No one can demand information regarding a person's private life. Private life is primarily an individual's freedom, where each person decides what information about their personal life can be made public. Private life includes family relationships, financial matters, health information, intimate life, and other aspects of a person's life. If these rights are violated, the citizen has the right to demand accountability, punishment through legal means, and compensation for moral damages.

- Everyone has the right to privacy of correspondence, telephone conversations, mail, electronic, and other messages. Therefore, interception of letters and other mail, as well as wiretapping of phone conversations, are prohibited. Searches, seizures, and imposition of arrest on correspondence, as well as wiretapping, can only be conducted on grounds and procedures established by the Criminal Procedure Code.

- Collection, storage, use, and dissemination of information about a person's private life without their consent are not allowed. Although this rule might seem to limit the right established by Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which grants everyone the freedom to seek and disseminate information, there is no contradiction between these norms. The absence of consent from the individual for the dissemination of information about them is the primary indicator of unlawfulness.

It is noteworthy that in socialist states, the term "personal life" is used instead of "private life" (similarly to "personal property" instead of "private property"). However, based on these formulations, it can be concluded that personal and private life are synonymous terms, defining the same phenomenon.

2. DISTINGUISHING HARASSMENT FROM COMPLIMENTS, FLIRTING, INSULTS, AND ASSAULTS

It is important not to confuse the terms "harassment," "compliments," and "flirting." The difference between harassment and other behaviors lies in several aspects. Flirting is always a two-way process, with equal positions of the participants, and rejection does not result in any consequences for the rejecting party. In the case of harassment, there is always a power imbalance. This means that the harassing party, by definition, feels more stable and unpunished. Actions can be classified as sexual harassment if the victim perceives the inappropriateness of such behavior, senses its aggressive undertone, and occupies a subordinate position relative to their harasser, somehow depending on their will (passenger and driver, student and examiner, subordinate and supervisor). These characteristics can be summarized in the following table:

Flirting, compliment	Harassment
1. It is not an encroachment on honor, dignity, personal inviolability and privacy;	1. It is an encroachment on honor, dignity, personal inviolability and privacy;
2. There is no dependence or imbalance of power, authority, status between the parties;	2. There is dependence or imbalance of power, authority, status between the parties;
3. The parties are on an equal footing;	3. The parties are not on an equal footing;
4. The process is mutual and bilateral;	4. The process is not mutual, and one-sided;
5. It takes place with the consent of the two parties;	5. Occurs without the consent of the other party;
6. Refusal does not entail consequences for the refused party;	6. Refusal entails consequences for the refused party;
7. It has a positive character;	7. It has a negative character;
8. Compliments and flirting follow from the customs of ethics and do not entail responsibility.	8. Harassment is regulated by law and entails liability.

In the United States and Europe, harassment is broadly interpreted as any unwanted sexual behavior. The National Institute of Justice of the U.S. Department of Justice includes both harassment and rape in the concept of "sexual violence." This position is also held by the World Health Organization.

Article 2, Point "B" of the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women, adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 20, 1993, regulates that violence against women includes various forms, such as physical, sexual, and psychological violence, including rape, sexual coercion, sexual harassment, and intimidation at work, in educational institutions, and in other places, as well as trafficking in women and forced prostitution.

According to the UN policy from April 2005, harassment is defined as any inappropriate and unwanted behavior that can reasonably be expected or perceived as causing offense or humiliation to another person. Harassment includes - but is not limited to - words, gestures, or actions that tend to annoy, alarm, insult, humiliate, intimidate, degrade, or cause personal humiliation or embarrassment to another person; or create an intimidating, hostile, or offensive work environment. It can involve a single incident or a series of incidents. Harassment can be intentional, unsolicited, and coercive.

Sexual harassment, according to this document, encompasses any unwanted sexual behavior, requests for intimate services, oral or physical behavior or gestures of a sexual nature, or any other behavior of a sexual nature that can reasonably be expected or perceived as offensive or humiliating to another person. Sexual harassment may occur when it interferes with work, is a condition of employment, or creates an intimidating, hostile, or offensive atmosphere. Both men and women can be victims or perpetrators of sexual harassment. Sexual harassment can also occur outside the workplace and/or outside working hours.

It is important to note that on February 11, 2008, the UN released a bulletin on the prohibition of discrimination, harassment, and abuse of position. It noted that both men and women can be both victims and perpetrators.

In the United States, the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) is in operation. It is a federal agency established in accordance with the Civil Rights Act of 1964 to administer and enforce civil rights laws against workplace discrimination. This organization has established the most extensive list of examples of harassment. In their guidelines, sexual harassment is categorized into two categories: verbal and non-verbal, as well as physical.

Verbal and non-verbal harassment are unwanted actions expressed as follows:

- Deliberately addressing a woman with diminutive or affectionate words;
- Whistling, including "catcalling" (calling and whistling like to a cat);
- Comments of a sexual nature, including comments about someone's clothing, anatomy, or appearance;
- Steering conversations toward intimate topics, including questions, jokes, hints about intimate life, preferences, or stories;
- Spreading lies or rumors about someone's personal intimate life;
- Sexual glances, gestures, or signals. For example, sounds of kissing and smacking, licking lips, winking, staring, facial expressions of a sexual nature;
- Messages of a sexual nature. These include letters, calls, or materials of a sexual nature such as photos and videos.

Physical harassment are unwanted actions expressed as follows:

- Touching another person's body, including their clothing or hair. This includes hugs, kisses, pats, caresses, and other actions that cause discomfort to the person;
- Frottage (rubbing against another person's body);
- Unwanted pressure or coercion for sexual favors.

Based on the above, it is necessary to differentiate between harassment, insults, and rape. Harassment violates personal integrity, honor, dignity, and private life. However, unlike insults, these violations of personal non-property rights are of a sexual nature. While the commentary to the Code of Administrative Offenses defines insult as an offense that infringes upon the honor and dignity of citizens, representing a negative assessment that undermines the moral prestige of the individual in the eyes of others and damages the respect for oneself by the victim.

Professor Rustambaev provides a similar definition, according to which an insult is an expressed in an indecent form negative assessment of the victim's personality, which has a generalized character, humiliates the honor and dignity of the individual, undermines their moral prestige both in the eyes of others and in their own eyes.

As derived from these interpretations, there are significant differences between these concepts, which are manifested in the following criteria:

Insults	Harassment
They are an encroachment on honor and dignity	They are an encroachment on personal inviolability, honor, dignity and privacy
It is not sexual in nature	They are of a sexual nature
The gender of the sides does not matter	As a rule, they occur from men to women, more rarely, on the contrary

Distinguishing harassment from rape is a complex issue. Despite being different types of assaults with varying consequences, many countries consider them part of the same problem. Researchers, practicing lawyers, and legislators agree that all forms of sexual violence harm individuals, families, and society. However, theoretically, rape involves sexual intercourse through violence, threats, or taking advantage of the victim's helplessness, primarily violating sexual freedom and integrity, potentially endangering the victim's life and health. In contrast, harassment, as mentioned earlier, primarily violates personal integrity, honor, dignity, and private life.

As part of a final qualification project and for analyzing harassment issues in Uzbekistan, a social survey was conducted using Google Forms, with 277 participants. Respondents were asked to define harassment, with 197 providing descriptions consistent with the aforementioned definitions. Additionally, they were asked about the difference between harassment, flirting, and compliments, yielding 199 responses.

3. THE PREVALENCE OF THE PROBLEM – STATISTICS FOR THE WORLD AND THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Illustrative data on sexual harassment underscores the prevalence of the issue:

- A study in the European Union involving 42,000 individuals revealed that every second woman (55%) had experienced sexual harassment at least once since the age of 15, with one in five women (21%) experiencing it within the 12 months prior to the study. Among those who experienced harassment since the age of 15, 32% indicated someone from their workplace, such as a colleague or supervisor, as the perpetrator.
- In a study conducted in South Africa, 77% of women reported experiencing sexual harassment at some point in their working lives.
- Approximately every second woman in Australia (53% or 5 million) has been subjected to sexual harassment by someone of either gender throughout their lives.
- Globally, it's estimated that 246 million girls and boys experience violence in schools annually, with evidence showing that girls are at greater risk of sexual violence, harassment, and exploitation than boys.
- 76% of female students from eight universities in Bangladesh reported instances of sexual harassment.
- In Spain, 62% of students witnessed or experienced some form of gender-based violence on campus.
- A global report revealed that nearly two-thirds of female journalists have experienced some form of intimidation, threats, or insults related to their work.

- 82% of female parliamentarians from 39 countries across five regions reported facing sexist or demeaning sexual remarks, gestures, or images, as well as threats and/or bullying, primarily through social media channels.

- In Washington, D.C., USA, a survey found that 27% of transit passengers experienced some form of sexual harassment.

- A baseline study in Kigali, Rwanda, showed that 55% of women were concerned about attending educational institutions after dark.

- A preliminary study in Port Moresby, conducted by UN Women, found that over 90% of women and girls experienced sexual violence in some form while using public transportation in 2013, including buses, waiting at bus stops, going to and from bus stops, or in taxis.

- An Australian survey of over 30,000 university students revealed that 32% of female students experienced sexual harassment on campus, compared to 17% of male students.

- According to Catalyst, an international women's rights organization, both women (80% of Americans and 50% of Europeans) and men (17% and 10%, respectively) become victims of such aggression. Moreover, in four out of five cases, the aggressors are men.

- Victims of harassment in relationships are not limited to women. According to a study by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention in the United States, 4.8% of men have experienced harassment from their partners.

Discussing the scope of harassment cannot overlook the "MeToo" movement—a public movement against sexual harassment, where victims shared their experiences. The phrase "MeToo" was initially used in this context on social media in 2006 by activist Tarana Burke, who survived sexual violence. By October 15, 2017, the hashtag had been used over 200,000 times on social media, and by October 16, it exceeded 500,000 uses. On Facebook, the hashtag was used by over 4.7 million people in 12 million posts within the first 24 hours. Facebook reported that 45% of users in the United States had at least one friend who posted this term.

In June 2020, UzNews.uz correspondent Malika Tursunova wrote an article about harassment in Uzbekistan. According to the survey, with over 1600 respondents:

- 91.5% believed it was dangerous for a girl to go out alone late at night, with responses indicating a fear of attracting unwanted attention.

- Out of 1615 respondents, 1330 were victims of harassment, with 215 experiencing it on a regular basis.

- Only 8% of women reported harassment to law enforcement.

Additionally, within the framework of writing a final qualification project, statistics on harassment in Uzbekistan were compiled. Out of 273 respondents, 230 (84.2%) indicated they or their close acquaintances had experienced harassment, while 43 (15.8%) stated they had not. When asked where harassment occurs most frequently, 175 respondents identified public transport, 170 mentioned public places, 73 cited educational institutions, and only 56 mentioned workplaces.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE LEGISLATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

When it comes to legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it's important to note that Article 46 of the Constitution specifies equal rights for women and men. Following Uzbekistan's accession to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) on August 18, 1995, and the initiation of gender policy reforms in our country, two crucial laws were enacted on September 2, 2019: "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" and "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence."

The law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" in Article 3 defines basic concepts and regulates forms of gender discrimination. According to it, direct gender discrimination includes any distinction, exclusion, or restriction aimed at denying women and men their rights and freedoms in all areas of societal life, including discrimination based on marital status, pregnancy, family responsibilities, as well as sexual harassment and unequal pay for equal work and qualifications.

Under Article 28 of this law, if a person believes they have been subjected to direct or indirect gender discrimination, they have the right to appeal to authorized bodies or the court. The legal issue lies in the lack of a clear and detailed definition of what constitutes harassment and what actions should be considered as an infringement on personal integrity, honor, dignity, and private life of a citizen in any legislative act of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Article 3 of the law "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" defines harassment as an action (or inaction) that humiliates the honor and dignity of women, including harassment, for which no administrative or criminal liability is provided. From this norm, it is emphasized by legislation that not only a more detailed definition of the term is absent in the Republic of Uzbekistan but also mechanisms of protection.

Article 4 of the aforementioned act prescribes the rights of victims of harassment and violence. According to it, victims of harassment and violence have the right to:

- Apply to relevant authorized bodies and organizations or the court with a statement regarding harassment and violence against them or threats thereof.
- Receive free legal advice, economic, social, psychological, medical, and other assistance at special centers, as well as through a toll-free hotline.
- Apply to law enforcement agencies demanding the issuance of a protection order, and in case of violation of the conditions of the protection order, inform them about it.
- Apply to the court demanding compensation for the material damage caused to them and compensation for moral harm due to harassment and violence.

Victims of harassment and violence, when applying to the court with a claim for compensation for the material damage caused to them and compensation for moral harm, are exempt from paying state fees.

The problem of applying these norms in practice remains open. The term "harassment" is mentioned in the Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court dated October 29, 2010, "On judicial practice in cases of rape and satisfaction of sexual needs in unnatural form", according to which harassment without the use of violence, threats, or the exploitation of the helpless state of the victim cannot be qualified under the articles on rape (Article 118 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) and violent satisfaction of sexual needs in unnatural form (Article 119 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

In current cases of harassment, courts apply the analogy of law and use other applicable articles. Article 1021 of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan states that moral damages are compensated by the perpetrator if they are at fault, particularly in cases where harm is caused by damaging information. Article 1022 specifies that compensation is in monetary form, determined by the court based on the victim's suffering and the perpetrator's fault. National law does not recognize harassment as a basis for moral damage compensation.

Both the Administrative Responsibility Code and the Criminal Code of Uzbekistan address insult. Insult, intentional humiliation, carries fines or community service. Repeat offenses or insult via media can lead to heavier penalties. However, applying these laws to harassment may be inappropriate.

Article 121 of the Criminal Code relates to coercion, primarily affecting a woman's sexual freedom. Compulsion involves unlawful pressure for sexual acts, punishable by community service or imprisonment. Despite legal complexities, reforms addressing harassment are underway in Uzbekistan, involving government and civil society collaboration.

5. LEGAL REGULATION OF HARASSMENT IN THE DEVELOPED WORLD

The USA. The official recognition of the term 'sexual harassment' in the USA began over 50 years ago. Initially introduced in the Civil Rights Act of 1964, sexual harassment was legally defined as a form of gender discrimination in 1980.

This amendment expanded women's rights to file lawsuits and seek compensation for harassment. In 1986, the landmark case of Mechelle Vinson led to the official acknowledgment of sexual harassment as a crime.

A pivotal moment in combating sexual harassment in the USA was the advocacy of women's rights activists in the 1990s. They raised awareness of harassment and sexism in the media, striving to counter gender inequality. In 1994, the Violence Against Women Act was signed, highlighting actions of a sexual nature as particularly undesirable. In 1998, two significant workplace harassment cases resulted in victories for the plaintiffs.

The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, also known as the Istanbul Convention, was adopted on May 11, 2011. It provided clear guidelines for European countries to work towards a region free from gender-based violence. Article 40 of the Convention defined harassment and urged member states to enact legal measures against it.

France. In 2018, France enacted a law imposing fines of up to 750 euros for sexist insults, demeaning comments, and 'sexual behavior' in public places. The fines are issued immediately to spare victims from lengthy legal processes. The first person fined was a man who insulted a woman's appearance on a suburban Paris bus.

Spain. In Spain, sexual harassment involving violence or threats is punishable by imprisonment for 1 to 5 years.

United Kingdom. Sexual harassment was recognized as a form of discrimination in 1986. The Discrimination Act defines harassment as unwanted behavior based on sex or of a sexual nature, creating a hostile or offensive environment. Penalties range up to 6 months imprisonment or fines, with Scotland imposing up to five years.

Switzerland. Prohibition of workplace sexual harassment is part of the Gender Equality Act since 1995. Employers are responsible for protecting employees' rights, mental and physical well-being, defining harassment as any behavior affecting human dignity, including threats, promises, coercion, or pressure for sexual purposes.

Denmark. Sexual harassment is defined as actions intending to change the victim's sexual status against their will, causing harm or diminished dignity. Both men and women are considered equal, making any attempt to alter this balance a form of harassment. Sexual jokes and comments at work are discriminatory only if explicitly stated in the company's policy. Women are responsible for resisting harassment.

Czech Republic. Harassment is unwanted sexual behavior in the workplace, deemed inappropriate, offensive, resisted, or perceived as a condition for employment decisions, primarily regulated by the Labor Code.

Not only in European countries but also in advanced nations across other continents, harassment is regulated by legislation. For instance, in Australia, the Sex Discrimination Act of 1984 defines sexual harassment as unwanted behavior in circumstances where a reasonable person would expect the targeted individual to feel offended, humiliated, or intimidated.

Israel. Israel's Sexual Harassment Law of 1998 broadly interprets sexual harassment, prohibiting behavior that could be perceived as discrimination, restriction of freedom, violation of human dignity, infringement of the right to respect and privacy, or retaliation for sexual harassment, with amendments in 2014 addressing the unauthorized dissemination of sexually explicit material.

India. Sexual harassment in India encompasses unwanted verbal or physical actions, sexual comments, physical contact, pornography exposure, demands or requests for sexual favors, or any other unwanted sexual behavior. The critical factor is the unwanted nature of the behavior, prioritizing its impact on the victim's well-being over the perpetrator's intention.

Philippines. The 1995 Law on Sexual Harassment primarily aims to protect and respect the dignity of workers, employees, applicants, and students in educational institutions or centers. It defines workplace, education, or training-related sexual harassment, outlines employer responsibilities, and sets penalties for violations.

Argentina. In April 2019, Argentina's Senate established accountability for harassment against women in public places (transport, shops, streets), punishable by fines ranging from 1000 to 15,000 pesos, covering both physical and verbal harassment.

Georgia. In May 2019, Georgia's parliament passed a law imposing fines of 300 to 500 laris and corrective labor for harassment, defined as unwanted sexual behavior causing intimidation, hostility, degradation, or offensive environments. 'Sexual behavior' includes sexually explicit remarks, genital display, and other verbal or non-verbal sexual conduct."

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ISSN: 2181-4031
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4031

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

II-ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ-II, НОМЕР 3

JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

VOLUME-II, ISSUE 3

«Фундаментал тадқиқотлар» электрон журнали 2022 йил 22 декабрь куни № 054837-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

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